

CLINICO – MORFOLOGICAL FEATURES OF BURN INJURIES CAUSED BY HIGH TEMPERATURES

Smolnițchi Daria

*Student, Faculty of General Medicine,
Nicolae Testemitanu
State University of Medicine and Pharmacy
Republic of Moldova, Chisinau*

Abstract

Burns are injuries to the skin or other organic tissues that are caused by the local action of high temperatures. The cause of burns can be: flame/explosion, hot liquids or gases, superheated or incandescent solids, electric current, chemicals agents and sunlight. There are 4 degrees of burns, depending on the intensity of the burn and its morphological aspects. The "palm area", conventionally equal to 1% of the body surface and the "rule of 9", are used to estimate the burned body surface. There are different scores to determine the severity and prognosis of burns, so: Baux, ABSI.

In the forensic diagnosis it is necessary to determine when the burn occurred - during life or after death (antemortem or postmortem burns).

Keywords: burns, injuries, burn shock, rule of nines.

Introduction:

The problem of burn injuries has been around for decades. Determining the nature and severity of injuries and damage to health, including burn injuries, is a necessary part of forensic examination. In forensic examination, full investigation of burns requires determination of their cause. They are frequently represented by thermal, electrical, chemical and radiation injuries. [13]

According to WHO data, an estimated 180 000 deaths each year are caused by burns - the vast majority occur in low- and middle-income countries. Burns usually occur at home due to people's own negligence in the home or workplace and are accidental. [17]

Definition, etiology and epidemiology:

Burns are injuries to the skin or other organic tissues that are caused by the local action of high temperatures. The etiology of burns can be presented by: flame/explosion, hot liquids, superheated or incandescent solids, electric current, chemicals agents and radiation. Burn injuries can lead to profound long-term damage, even if the wounds have healed, affecting not only physical health but also mental health and quality of life. [3,6,18]

Risk factors in burns include: gender, age, socio-economic factors, etc. In most countries, men are injured almost twice as often as women. The exception to this trend was seen in Ghana and India, where three times as many women are injured and die from burns as men. Women are usually affected in kitchens. Thermal burns often occur from local exposure to substances with high temperatures, such as: spilling containers of hot liquids (water, oil), from exploding stoves or preparing dishes over an open fire, which can ignite clothing. Open flames used for heating and lighting are also a risk factor. Men are more prone to burns at work due to flames in fires, chemical and electrical burns. [10,13] Children are particularly vulnerable to burns. Although a major risk is inadequate adult supervision. Other risk factors involved in the development and frequency of burns include: carelessness while performing household chores, such as preparing dishes and caring for young children; overcrowding, poverty and lack of adequate safety measures; alcohol abuse and smoking.[10]

Burns classification:

Pic. 1. Burn depth. [10]

Mechanisms by which burns cause death:

- Burn shock
- Infection
- Pneumonia
- Septicemia
- Toxic shock syndrome
- Pulmonary embolism
- Gastric ulceration
- Acute renal failure
- Scar-related malignancy. [7]

Severe burns will develop **combustion sickness**, which often becomes the cause of death. The severity of the disease, its development and prognosis will influence the area of deep burns. Also an important role belongs to the age and location of the lesion. [14]

Four periods are highlighted in the development of combustion disease:

- ✓ Shock period
- ✓ Period of toxemia
- ✓ Period of septicotoxemia
- ✓ Period of reconvalescence

“**Burn shock** describes the rapidly developing hypovolemic circulatory failure seen in the first 72 hours after burn injury. Skin burning is followed by

hypovolemia, low cardiac output, hypoproteinemia, hyponatremia, and a rising hematocrit. Burn shock is the result of hypovolemia and the effects of cytokines and other inflammatory mediators”. [7] In the first hours the patient may be excited, due to pain syndrome and psycho-emotional stress, later he becomes apathetic and lethargic. Oliguria develops at the onset of combustion sickness, but in severe states anuria. [1,2,11,14]

The second period is the period of **toxemia**, which will develop in the 2, 3 days and continue for 10 to 14 days after the trauma. Clinical manifestations: fever 38 - 39°C; CNS disorders, characterised by: headache, lethargy, sleep disorder, delirium, hallucinations, lack of appetite; anemia, oliguria, polyuria, hyperproteinemia. After the period of 15, 16 days, clinically the symptoms of toxemia decrease. [2,11,14]

The period of **septicemia** is characterised by the development of infection. After the scab detaches, various infections join and septic-purulent complications occur. The period of septicotoxemia may end with complete recovery of the skin. But in cases of severe burns, the period of septicotoxemia is accompanied by loss of body weight, dryness and pallor of the skin, severe muscle atrophy, scars. [2,14]

The recovery period, is the fourth period of the combustion disease, for which it is characteristic: normalization of the functions of organs and systems affected during the previous periods. It ends with reconvalescence or death. [14]

Estimating the surface area of the body burned:

Pic. 2. Rule of nines. [5,7]

According to "rule of nines", the head represents 9% of the body surface, each upper limb 9% of the body surface, each lower limb 18% of the body surface, the anterior trunk 18%, the posterior trunk 18%, the perineum (genital area) 1% of the body surface. To assess the degree of burns and to obtain the percentage of body surface burnt, the values are added together. [12]

In the case of children, the "rule of 9" is that the head represents 18% of the body surface and both legs together represent 28% of the body surface. [12]

Antemortem versus Postmortem burns:

- Antemortem: Presence of soot in the airways, alveoli and sphenoid sinuses (Pic. 3)
- Presence of carboxyhemoglobin in blood
- Presence of a red rim to a burn
- Significant presence of dystrophic and necrotic changes of nerve elements
- Presence of thrombi in the vessels of the affected areas
- The evaluation of phlyctene detects the presence of high numbers of leukocytes and fibrin in the exudate. [8,16]

Pic. 3. Soot in airway. [15]

Postmortem:

- The Pugilistic Position - hands raised in front of the face (Pic. 4)
- Skin splitting
- Fractures
- Heat Hematoma. [7]

Pic. 4. Pugilistic attitude. [15]

The **Baux score** were developed for determination of the prognosis of burns according to burned body surface area and age. Is represented by the formula:

$$A+S=P \quad (1)$$

where A represents age, S -burned body surface area and P - probability of death.

The prognosis is:

- favourable if the score is < 60
- relatively favourable, if the score is < 80
- reserved, if the score is > 75
- extremely severe, if the score is > 100. [4,9]

Conclusion: Every year, millions of people suffer from burns and hundreds of thousands die from them. Burn injuries present challenging problems to the forensic physician and pathologist. Medico-legal problems of burns include: positive diagnosis of burns, assessment of the burned area, determination of the time of burn (intravital or postmortem) and assessment of the cause of death.

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